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Francesco Stella (✉ francesco.stella@epfl.ch)

EPFL <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4724-1886>

Mickael Achkar

EPFL <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9135-8996>

Cosimo Della Santina

TU Delft

Josie Hughes

CREATE Lab, EPFL

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PAWS: A Synergy-Based Robotic Quadruped Leveraging Passivity for Robustness and Behavioural Diversity

Francesco Stella^{1,2*}, Mickaël M. Achkar^{1*}, Cosimo Della Santina^{2,3}, Josie Hughes¹

¹CREATE Lab, STI, EPFL, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.

²Department of Cognitive Robotics, Delft University of Technology, 2628 CD Delft, The Netherlands.

³Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics, German Aerospace Center (DLR), 82234 Wessling, Germany.

* These authors contributed equally. Corresponding author: francesco.stella@epfl.ch

Quadrupedal animals show remarkable capabilities in traversing diverse terrains and display a range of behaviors and gait patterns. Achieving similar performance is a key goal for robotics researchers. We propose a bio-inspired approach to the design of quadrupeds that seeks to exploit the body and the passive properties of the robot. Using this novel approach we develop *PAWS*, a Passive Automata With Synergies. By leveraging the principles of motor synergies, the design incorporates variable stiffness, biological anatomical insights, and self-organization to simplify control while maximizing its capabilities. The resulting synergy-based quadruped requires only four actuators and exhibits emergent, animal-like dynamical responses, including robustness to environmental perturbations and a wide range of behaviors. The finding contributes to the development of machine intelligence, and provides robots with more efficient and natural-looking robotic locomotion by combining synergistic ac-

tuation, compliant body properties, and embodied compensatory strategies.

1 Introduction

Quadruped animals demonstrate advanced, efficient locomotion strategies across diverse terrains leveraging a range of behaviors, including varied gait patterns (1). Illustratively, cheetahs reach over 70 mph, mountain goats maneuver steep, rocky landscapes, and kangaroos can leap distances exceeding 7 m. The development of robotic quadrupeds seeks to replicate, or exceed, the capabilities for applications including exploration, inspection, and search and rescue (2, 3). The capabilities of animals stem from their unique morphological characteristics and passive biomechanical and musculoskeletal properties (4). Compliance mediated by elastic tendons and muscles is widely recognized as a central driver of this observed physical intelligence (5, 6). Yet, the mainstream approach to robotic locomotion is not to replicate the physical functionality of animal systems, but to approximate the biomechanics and morphology, relying on standard rigid robotic components in conjunction with series elastic actuators (7, 8). The task of implementing effective locomotion is then fully outsourced to complex model-based (9, 10) or a learnt locomotion strategy (11–13). The results achieved this way are indubitably impressive. However, they require significant amounts of computation, rapid sensory-motor feedback loops, dense networks of sensors, and full actuation to function properly.

A diametrically opposite approach is followed by proponents of (bipedal) passive walkers. These simplified systems utilize their structure, compliance, and environmental interactions to achieve simple yet robust, energy efficient, ‘brain-less’ passive walking (14, 15). However, despite the early encouraging results, as of today, (semi-)passive walkers remain more of an intriguing proof-of-concept rather than fully-fledged robots (16, 17). With their limited¹ number of degrees of freedom (DoF), even when partially actuated (19), they show limited versatility

¹Passive walkers with more than a few DoFs have been only analyzed in theory (18) but never realized.

and behavioural diversity which hinders any realistic application or deployment. To overcome this, increasingly we are seeing encouraging results from approaches that exploit bioinspiration and, more specifically, physical, compliance-driven embodied intelligence (20) for robotic locomotion (21–24). Recent examples include the excitation of natural jumping locomotion in a cat-inspired robotic leg in (25), the dragonfly-larvae-inspired compliant robot that can emulate a synchronized dual-catapult system for ballistic movements in (26), a quadruped with a feline-like multi-joint spine for high-speed running (27), and *Birdbot*, an ostrich inspired robot relying upon a clutch-based mechanism yielding efficient locomotion (28).

With the goal of achieving complex and versatile quasi-passive gaits with full-fledged quadrupedal robots, we look to nature for inspiration. More specifically, we augment passivity and compliance with the other fundamental ingredient of animal neuro-mechanics: the hierarchical reduction of complexity through synergistic mappings (29, 30). Rather than directly actuating all degrees of freedom of the animal body, the central nervous system generates coordinated patterns of activation called *synergies*. This way, it actuates only the directions that are important, leaving it to the body’s physical intelligence to generate the rest of the motion. As a control principle, synergies have been applied to hands (31–33), supernumerary limbs (34), robotic arms (35), and exoskeletons (36). Arguably the most successful application of synergies has been as a principle of embodying intelligence into mechanical design. In this context, synergistic actuation has found substantial application in robotic hands (37–41), yielding devices that can grasp and manipulate objects with minimal sensing and control requirements, while using only a few actuation sources (typically one to four). However, to date, synergistic actuation has not been applied to locomotion.

In this work, we present *PAWS*, the first legged system with synergistic actuation which uses 4 actuators to control its 12 degrees of freedom. The four motors implement four locomotion synergies that we distill from biological data of dogs running. By combining synergy-based

actuation with optimal physical compliance, this quadruped shows emergent and animal-like dynamical responses to the environment. PAWS shows fully passive locomotion gaits across all its multi-articulated legs which are robust to environmental perturbations and present behavioral diversity. Using inverse kinematics on motor synergies, we can also generate versatile active gaits like sitting, jumping, and running.

This design is fueled by a pipeline where optimal actuation synergies and passive compliance are identified based on biological quadruped motion capture data. From these, a synergy-based actuation is extracted to mimic the neuromechanical couplings seen in biological systems. We observe that this solution yields directional stiffness at the leg’s end effector which varies across the robot’s workspace or gait in an advantageous way. The synergistic tendon routing yields limb coupling, enabling embodied compensatory strategies and behaviors emerging purely from the system’s mechanical response. The system’s passive traits offer environmental resilience due to the bio-inspired spatial stiffness and leg coupling. This provides a new, bio-inspired approach to the design of quadrupeds which seeks to exploit environmental interactions.

2 Results

By designing a robotic quadruped with motor synergies and compliance, we seek to develop a minimally actuated robot that shows robustness to disturbances and behavior diversity. To generate this design, we find inspiration from the neuromechanical couplings displayed by biological systems. By translating animal joint motion recordings into the principle components that best describe the motions, we can extract the synergies and grouping of legs that enable replication with minimal loss of reachable poses. Following this dimensionality reduction, the joint stiffness and tendon routings for a 12-joint tendon-driven quadruped robot can be identified through evolutionary optimization. By combining this design pipeline with modular hardware, we can show that by appropriately designing the impedance and postural synergies, it is pos-

Figure 1: **a)** PAWS, a Passive Automata with Synergies, together with a pictorial representation of the features contributing to the high embodied intelligence of the design. **b)** Schematic representation of the pipeline used to design and control PAWS. From real-world animal data, linear order-reduction methods are used to extract the synergies. These are then used as input to an optimization of the mechanical components and to find the motor activations for the synergistic system.

sible to generate a synergy-enabled robotic quadruped that displays robust passive interaction with the environment and diverse and natural-looking active behaviors. Namely, we develop PAWS, the first synergy-based quadruped which leverages only four actuators to control all 12

joints (3 per leg). We experimentally characterize the passive and actuated properties of this novel robot, showing the emergent robustness and rapid recovery to perturbations and also the actuated capabilities of the system.

2.1 Synergy Analysis from Animal Data

There is extensive evidence that the sensory-muscular systems of animals are organized into functional or structural synergies at different hierarchical levels including at the neural and muscular levels (43). Mirroring this neuromechanical coupling in robotic systems would be hugely insightful however is challenging in terms of data availability and technologies. Instead, we propose identifying motor synergies from observations of the animals' kinematics, and exploring the extent to which this can provide physically advantageous behaviors whilst reducing the control complexity.

To capture the forms of motion and poses seen in animals we use an open source data-set composed of 147,541 poses and corresponding joint angles acquired via motion capture of a dog (42). Some exemplar poses and motions are illustrated in Fig. 2c. This set of postures and motions is highly redundant, as many poses show similar ratios of joint activations. This redundancy can be captured using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), where we decompose the animals' joint data into a number of components that seek to represent the maximum amount of variance in the animal joint data. This PCA-based dimensionality reduction was conducted by identifying the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of the dog data set on the recorded joint motions for different possible sub-sets of limbs, including all four limbs, and different two limb combinations. When analyzing the full body, 12 joints (3 joints per leg) were considered, resulting in a 12×12 synergy matrix, with the columns representing the principal components. PCA was also conducted on different 2-legged groupings of the 4 legs, to explore how different limb couplings affect the variance captured via PCA. Specifically, we focus on hind and fore-

Figure 2: **a**) Eigenvectors of the PCA for different dog limb groupings ranked by explained variance. The eigenvectors highlighted show potential candidates for a physical system with a reduced actuation and yet a wide range of reachable behaviors. **b**) At the top, the evolution of the first two principal components, described as Synergy 1 and 2, as extracted from PCA. In the middle, the evolution of the two synergies after the optimization, i.e. considering the losses due to the mechanical design specifications, but not considering the deployment on a real system. At the bottom, the evolution shown by the real system when actuating only one of the motors. **c**) Example of poses from the data-set from (42). **d**) Schematic representation of the mechanism of each leg. Each joint is composed of two pulleys to guide the tendons for synergy s_1 and s_2 and a torsional stiffness module. **e**) A highlight of the torsional stiffness module with the force transmission highlighted. This is composed of two linear springs acting antagonistically on a rotational pulley. Thanks to the transmission system, a wide set of pulley radii can be accommodated, thus enabling a wide set of possible torsional stiffnesses achievable with the module. **f**) A representation of the mechanism found as a solution of the optimization, considering tendon routing, pulley sizes and stiffness at the joint level.

limbs, right and left limbs, and crossed limbs. For these, we consider 6 joints, and two 6×6 synergy matrices. For each of these analyses, the extracted principle components were ranked based on explained variance. We consider what explained variance can be captured with four synergies (i.e. four components for the four legs, and the first two for each 2 leg configuration). The results are given in Fig. 2a, where we see for all configurations, four synergies can be used to achieve upwards of $\approx 80\%$ across all legs.

When all four limbs are considered, four synergies can provide $\approx 88\%$ explained variance. Whilst this is comparatively very high, it is accompanied by the realization challenges of having shared tendons across four legs. Separating fore and hindlimbs leads to an undesirable disparity in the explained variance between the two limbs, with a lower performance for the forelimbs. Having synergies for left and right limbs, or the crossed limbs provides a similar overall performance $\approx 81\%$, we select to use the synergies with separate left and right limbs, as this simplifies the mechanical design and implementation. With this selected synergy and limb groups, an upper bound of the achievable variance of the motion set can be identified as 79% when using only four actuators, i.e. integrating two synergies per half body.

2.2 Realization and transfer to a synergy-equivalent mechanism

To realize the design, the quadruped is modeled as having four legs, each with three joints. Each ‘half-dog’ (i.e. one forelimb and hindlimb), has 2 motors connected via a pulley to the two tendons which route each synergy. Each tendon is guided by a set of pulleys left free to rotate around the centre of rotation of each joint (Fig. 2d). Each joint is connected to the subsequent link through a torsional spring, encapsulated in the mechanism depicted in Fig. 2e. The robot design is composed of modular parts, in which the radius of the pulleys guiding each tendon, the direction of the tendon routing and the torsional stiffness for each joint can be fully parametrized and rapidly customized. Given the selected number and distribution

of the synergies, an optimization process reported in Sec. 4.2, is performed to generate the tendon routing, pulley sizes and joint stiffness to best achieve the identified synergies. The cost function for the optimization is designed so to penalize differences in joint activations between the synergy base and the resulting motion of the mechanism. The evolution of the joints in the real system is formalized as the static equilibrium between the torsional springs embedded at the joint level and the tension exerted by the multi-articular tendons. Therefore, by varying tendon routing, pulley sizes and joint stiffness it is possible to achieve different motions as a function of the tendon activation of the motors. A schematic representation of the resulting optimized robot, topology and synergy routing is shown in Fig. 2f. The design has a high stiffness in its front foot and rear hip, and a lowest stiffness in the rear foot and hip showing an inverse distribution of stiffness between the fore and hindlimbs.

Given the identified design of the robot from the optimization process, the matching to ideal synergies obtained from the animal data in both simulation and on the real-world hardware can be evaluated. In Fig. 2b and in Video S1, the simulated motion path enabled by the two independent synergies is shown for that directly from PCA (top), a simulation after the optimization process (centre) and finally deployed in the real world on the robotic hardware (bottom). Here each synergy is activated and the ‘foot’ pose of the robot is captured via simulation or video tracking. It can be seen that synergy 1 provides predominantly hindlimb motion, whereas synergy 2 provides mostly forelimb motion, however, there is some coupling between them. The optimization step introduces marginal error in comparison to the PCA results with a loss in joint couplings of 8% and 4% for the first and second synergy respectively. There is also some additional coupling between the legs. When deploying the structure to the real world there is a close similarity in the expected motion path, however, the fore and hindlimb coupling is further extenuated for both synergies. This is most likely due to the optimization constraint of having all the joints coupled. This gap can be quantitatively assessed by measuring the joint activa-

tion (i.e. the ratio between motor activation and joint motion) for each synergy (Fig. S 9a). These results show a close mapping for both synergies in joint space, with the optimization step appearing to cause the largest discrepancies.

Despite the limited number of actuators present in the half-dog, the two synergies can be blended together to achieve a wide workspace, as shown in Video S1. The extent of this workspace was visualized by systematically blending the synergies with varying ratios and recording the pose of the two feet with motion capture (Fig. S9b). The hindlimb has a much larger workspace than the forelimb, in particular in the front-back direction.

2.3 Gait Inverse Kinematics

By performing the inverse kinematic (IK) within the workspace of the robot, it is possible to generate motor activation for each of the synergies that generate different bio-inspired animal gaits. Starting from motion capture of the animal, the target gait motion is defined by their front and back end-effector (paw) motion for a period or sequence of this gait. This motion is scaled to the size of the robot, and IK is performed in synergy space. Three key examples of different gait patterns are shown in Fig. 3a for walking, sitting and running, with the target animal-inspired gait, and that obtained from IK using only 2 synergies. Despite the reduced actuation set, the robot can track the different end-effector defined gaits. This is particularly notable given the robot and biological gait robots do not have an identical morphology.

The inverse kinematics considers only the Cartesian position of the end of the two legs, however, to fully leverage the synergy and IK based upon the bio-inspired gait, the means and route through which this gait is achieved are important. This can be measured by comparing the evolution of the six joint angles between the animal data and that of the robot, as given in Fig. 3b for the walking gait. Despite the IK considering only the end effector and the robot having some differences in morphology, the evolution of the robot's joint angles shows clear

similarities to the animal data. This is particularly the case for joints 3 and 4, which correspond to the hip and shoulder. The robot's knee joints (q_2 and q_5) clearly capture the pattern, although there is a minor difference in the timing. Finally, the ankle joints (q_1 and q_6) of the robot once again show a similar pattern of behavior with some offsets in the timing. This correspondence in both cartesian and joint space between animal and robot demonstrates how the synergy basis assists in implicitly capturing the gait and also the evolution by which the redundant leg system reaches a Cartesian position. This evolution can be beneficial in terms of efficiency, robustness and adaptability when walking (44).

2.4 Passive Properties

In addition to being able to achieve bio-inspired gaits and motions, by optimizing the design using animal motion the design captures advantageous passive properties. Namely, robustness to external perturbations and a passive gait pattern. Whilst direct actuation of the robot is necessary for functionality, and this can augment the passive response, by embedding advantageous properties at the hardware level, this can offload the computation required for such tasks to the body. The passive properties of the robot can be experimentally explored by placing the robot on a treadmill, counterbalancing the robot with masses such that it stabilized, and observing the response to different treadmill speeds or various external disturbances. The robot still has the synergy-based tendon routings but without direct connections to the motors, such that the fore and hindlimbs are connected directly. This experimental setup is shown in Fig. 5a.

When the four-legged passive robot is placed on the moving treadmill, there is an emergent periodic galloping-like gait that shows co-ordination between the fore and hindlimbs. This passive response is shown in Fig. 4a (top), showing the leg motion and rise and fall of the robot. When compared to the running motion of a dog (Fig. 4a (bottom)) we see similarities in the motion of the robot, with the passive properties mirroring a typical running gait.

Figure 3: **a)** Examples of behaviors that are possible to track with the reduced motor set. In particular, in gray the trajectories recorded on real animals are reported, while in red it is possible to observe the tracking achievable with the robotic system. **b)** Evolution of each of the 6 joints during a walking gait. In gray, the evolution of the joint on real-world animal data is reported with a confidence level based on the variation over multiple cycles. In red, the joint evolution for the robotic system, generated by solving the inverse kinematic problem on the synergy base. As demonstrated by the matching, by solving the inverse kinematic problem on the synergy subspace, we force the redundant kinematic of the system to reach Cartesian positions with poses that are biologically significant.

For the passive properties to provide advantageous robustness and also enable a variety of motions, it is important that the passive response varies for different external inputs to the system. This can be simulated by varying the speed of the treadmill and observing the resultant gait. By tracking the 'paws' of the robot via feature tracking of videos, the foot trajectories and

Figure 4: Passive response of the robotic system to external excitation. **a)** Emergent evolution of the robotic system when excited by the interaction with the treadmill. Thanks to the inter-joint mechanical couplings and the compliant interaction, the emergent leg evolution well matches the biological counterpart. **b)** Trajectories emergent of the paws corresponding to different levels of energy provided by the environment, parameterized with the speed of the treadmill. The repetitiveness of the trajectories proves the stability of the locomotion pattern over a variety of environmental conditions. **c)** Analysis of the emerging locomotion pattern. Both horizontal and vertical variations of the amplitude as a function of the speed. **d)** Analysis of the footfall pattern as a function of the period. Notably, different levels of excitation lead to different, stable, locomotion strategies, defined by varying levels of stance and flight time.

hence the footfall of the emergent gait can be recorded. To simplify the tracking of the feet this is performed with a ‘half-dog’. The resultant trajectories are shown in Fig. 4b for an increase in treadmill speed from 1 km/h through to 6 km/h, with the trajectory given relative to the top of the robot. The trajectories show a similar form, however, the amplitude of motion increases with treadmill speed and in particular for the forelimb. The hysteresis in the gait also grows, with the recovery stroke lower than the outward. This shows similarities to biological quadrupeds running with increasing speed, with the forelimb moving further forward to achieve a larger stroke to sustain the increase in speed. Fig. 4c reports the amplitude of the gait with increasing treadmill speed for the forelimb and hindlimb, showing a faster increase in forelimb amplitude, whereas the hindlimb increases until reaching a plateau at approximately 4 km/h. Unlike the passive dynamic walker which has rather a fixed gait in response to stimuli, the introduction of synergistic coupling and directional stiffness provides diversity in the response to stimuli, providing scaffolding for more complex actuated behaviors.

The gait can also be analyzed in terms of the footfall, to identify the progression between single support (single foot contact), double support (double foot contact) and flight period that occurs. By analyzing the trajectory and contact with the treadmill, the contact time for the fore and hindlimbs can be determined for a period of the passive motion. This footfall analysis is shown in Fig. 4d for different treadmill speeds. The progression from a single support to double and then flight periods matches the progression seen in dog gaits. Furthermore, with increasing treadmill speed we see a significant reduction in the single and double support periods, with much of the gait period forming the flight component of the stance. This shows that for varying treadmill speeds we see the emergence of different behavioral patterns and gait forms, where the synergies and design of the body determine this motion. Moreover, the emergent contact profiles match locomotion strategies in biological quadrupeds, which show increasingly shorter stance phases for faster locomotion strategies (45, 46). This emergent robust and animal-like

passive response is highly dependent on the correct deployment of the synergy theory on the mechanical design. Indeed, a change in routing direction in any of the joints leads to immediate failure of the passive gait pattern.

2.4.1 Response to perturbations

A second property observed in animals where passivity contributes is robustness to perturbation. As perturbation can occur rapidly, having a response that is not reliant on the brain provides robustness and a speed of response that enables behaviors to resume rapidly. We can explore the robust properties of the system by passively exciting the robot using the treadmill and applying various forms of disturbance and perturbation. Using the setup shown in Fig. 5a, further discussed in Sec. 4.7, various disturbances can be applied to the legs or body of the robot (Fig. 5b).

To quantitatively analyze the response of the passive robot to disturbances the half-dog robot is placed on the treadmill at a speed of 4 km/h and perturbations are applied to the forelimb, body and hindlimb (Fig. 5c). The trajectory of both feet is recorded prior to perturbation, during and after. For all disturbances, the gait rapidly returns to the limit cycle behavior observed prior to perturbation. For the forelimb perturbation, this is particularly evident, with the external influence causing a large offset of the forelimb, and a small coupled response in the forelimb. By the next period, the steady-state gait trajectory is observed with minimal differences. Similarly, for the body perturbation which causes a perturbation in both legs, there is a high robustness, with a rapid return to the previous gait cycle. Finally, the response of the hindlimb, which is stiffer at the hip level and hence requires more energy to be displaced, is slower, taking approximately four gait cycles to return to steady state behavior, as more energy is stored in the system.

In addition to the robustness to external perturbations, the ability to overcome obstacles

Figure 5: Dynamic response of PAWS to external perturbations. **a**) Experimental platform used to capture the performance of the system for both the half and full-body versions. A four-bar linkage connects the robot to a fixed support while the treadmill excites the system. A weight of 1.5 and 3 Kg is applied at the end of the four-bar linkage for the half and full-body version respectively to partially compensate gravitational forces. **b**) A set of exemplary perturbations applied to the system, which demonstrates passive and coordinated response, as in Video S3. **c**) Trajectories of fore and hind foot when perturbed at the ankle level or at the center of the body. After a transient, highlighted in red, the robot returns to the dynamic passive walking cycle. **d**) On the left, a timestamp of the dynamic response of the system to obstacles of different heights placed on the treadmill. On the right, the success rate as a function of the obstacle height, recorded on 30 experiments per obstacle.

within the environment is widely seen in quadrupedal animals. By placing obstacles of varying heights on the treadmill at random intervals the response to these obstacles and the success rate can be measured. Fig. 5d (top) shows a time lapse of the response of the dog to disturbances to the forelimb, and Fig. 5d (bottom) disturbances to the hindlimb. In both cases, the passivity and compliance in the system allow the robot to robustly overcome the obstacles in a manner that appears bio-inspired in nature. The mean success rate across 30 trials was measured for obstacles of different heights, and we see that lower obstacles (20mm) can be overcome purely by leveraging the passivity and compliance of the system. With the increase in height of the compliance, the success rate drops, with only 65% of 60mm obstacles being successfully overcome. These objects correspond to 20% of the height of the robot and suggest that as with animals, for obstacles of a certain height, the response requires active control in addition to passivity and compliance.

2.5 Stiffness-profiles and mechanical couplings

Mechanical impedance plays a central role in the interaction between the biological systems and the environment (47). To better understand the inherent robustness of the system to external perturbations and environmental excitations, we perform an analysis of the Cartesian stiffness profiles across the workspace of the robot. To quantitatively evaluate the reaction of the system to external perturbation, the robot body was fixed, and the end effector of a Franka Emika Panda robotic arm was secured to one of the paws. While one paw was forced to a grid of poses from the manipulator, the other was left free. As a result, for each pose, the robotic system reaches the equilibrium between the perturbation exerted by the manipulator and the physical impedance defined by the tendon-stiffness system in the robot's body. A camera was placed perpendicularly to the plane of motion to record the resulting displacement of the free paw due to mechanical couplings. The experimental setup is visualized in Fig. 10a. By perturbing the

half-dog foot with a given force via the arm along two perpendicular directions and measuring the disturbance, the local stiffness ellipsoid can be evaluated in Cartesian space as shown in Fig. S10a (center). During the experiment, both the displacement $\Delta x \in R^{3 \times v}$ of the paw and the reaction forces $F \in R^{3 \times v}$ were recorded, with v the number of samples per experiment. Hence, the experimental ellipsoid matrix $K_{\text{exp}} \in R^{3 \times 3}$ is evaluated by minimizing the least square error as $K_{\text{Experiment}} = F \Delta x^\dagger$.

The experimental results show significant variations in both the magnitude and direction of stiffness ellipsoids across the workspace. This result becomes more significant when overlapping locomotion trajectories in the workspace, as described in 4.6. As shown in the Walking example in Fig. S10a (right), the impedance of the legs is higher and perpendicular to the trajectory at extremes of the workspace, while it becomes parallel to the trajectory and more compliant in the central part of the workspace. Therefore, during the stance phase, the system is stiffer in the direction of the ground, as to sustain self-weight, while in the flight zone, the end effector stiffness becomes lower so as to react compliantly to perturbations.

This embodied impedance strategy is a result of the relevant submanifold used to solve the inverse kinematic. Indeed, as the end effector position is achieved in a natural fashion, as shown in Sec. 2.3, the configuration-dependent component of the Cartesian stiffness, formalized by the JJ^\top mapping, reflects biological strategies seen in animal-environment interactions.

2.5.1 Mechanical couplings

The synergistic routing of the tendons provides mechanical coupling between the fore and hindlimbs. This means when an external disturbance or force is applied to one leg, there is a physically coupled response in the other leg. The response depends on the configuration of the robot and the direction and magnitude of the external displacement. This mechanical coupling can be beneficial in terms of co-ordination between legs when responding to disturbances

of environmental factors.

To visualize this response we apply an external force to one foot, and measure the displacement in the second foot that arises from the mechanical coupling as shown in Fig.S 10b. When the forelimb is displaced forward, we see a coupled movement of the hindlimb backward and down. The coupled response is much lower when the forelimb is pushed backward, with a response more vertically down in the hindlimb. This coupling could assist in overcoming obstacles; when there is a disturbance of obstacle in the forelimb, the hindlimb corresponds, moving down and back to maintain stability.

When the hindlimb is disturbed, the response is somewhat minimal except for when the leg is moved horizontally forwards, with the forelimb showing a considerable horizontal motion. Once again, this could prove beneficial to the external disturbances and reflects the trajectories observed in Fig. 5c.

These experiments highlight the sensitivity of the coupling to both the pose of the robot and the direction of the external force applied. For certain conditions, the magnitude of resultant coupled displacement can be somewhat large, and can significantly affect the behavior of the robot. The specific directionality observed can help explain the robustness to recovery seen in Fig. 5.

2.6 Behaviour Diversity of the Full Quadruped

By combining the passive properties obtained from the optimized design and the synergy routing, with direct actuation, we leverage the passive properties whilst expanding the behavioral diversity of the system. This can enable a deployable, passive, synergy-enabled quadruped which can show a number of different gaits with only four independently controlled actuators.

The robot can be actuated using motor activations generated via IK for different motions. In Fig. 6a, it is possible to see the tracking of an actuated walking gait trajectory performed on

Figure 6: Different actuated behaviors demonstrated by PAWS. **a)** A comparison between the active and passive trajectories of the half-dog, shown relative to the ground, both moving at a treadmill speed of 1 km/h. **b)** The gait pattern changes over time when encountering an obstacle, showing how the legs' coupling causes perturbations to be reflected in the opposite leg. **c)** The robotic system transitioning between quasi-static poses, such as crouching, standing and forward leaning, thus demonstrating to support its own self-weight. **d)** PAWS, supported by tendons for self-stability, is actuated with the signals extracted with the inverse kinematic to perform a walking pattern. **e)** Motor activation is triggered on top of passive dynamic walking to start a jump, followed by a robust passive recovery and run.

the treadmill setup, and how it compares to the purely passive gait at the same speed. Notably, thanks to the actuation, the amplitude of the gait can be increased in both horizontal and vertical directions. This leads to better performances when interacting with unstructured terrains. When comparing actuated and passive gaits in the robustness to obstacles experiment seen in Fig. 5d, the actuated gait allows higher obstacles to be overcome.

Notably, during actuated gaits, the passive properties of disturbance rejection are preserved thanks to underactuation and distributed compliance. In Fig. 6b, the legs are tracked in Cartesian space, before, during and after fore and hindlimb perturbation due to the contact with a 3 Kg obstacle. It is possible to observe that, before the perturbation, the actuation enforces a periodic and stable walking gait. Yet the passivity-based robustness is still observable. The gait, perturbed by the contact with an obstacle on the fore and hindlimb respectively, rapidly and robustly returns to the previous actuated pattern. These results highlight the benefits of combining the passive properties of the robot's body with synergy based actuation.

To further demonstrate the versatility of synergistic actuation, four varying gaits have been selected from the animal data set, and synergy activations are extracted to best track the trajectories of these. Fig. 6c shows crouching, standing and forward leaning motions on the fully free-standing PAWS robot. As shown by the relative dog poses, these configurations closely mirror the bio-inspired poses from which they are obtained. Moreover, the experiment demonstrates the ability of the compliant body to fully support its own weight, while remaining compliant to mechanical perturbations.

In Fig. 6d, it can be observed that the freestanding robot exhibits an actuated walking gait, where the activations of the walking synergies shown in Fig. 3a are utilized in an out-of-phase manner between each half-dog. Using these signals derived from inverse kinematics, PAWS, supported by tendons to maintain its self-stability, is able to execute a synchronized and coordinated walking pattern on unstructured terrain.

Ultimately, passive and active behaviors can be combined. For example, in Fig. 6e, from the passive galloping behavior which emerges from the interaction with the treadmill, a jumping gait can be triggered by actuating the motors at a high frequency during the onset of the hindlimb contact.

This variety of gaits, encompassing crouching, standing, forward leaning motions, as well as the ability to transition from passive galloping to jumping and actuated walking, exemplifies the wide spectrum of behaviors attainable with minimal actuation. By leveraging the passive properties and synergy-based actuation, the PAWS robot demonstrates how passivity and minimal actuation can effectively resolve environmental interactions and enable the execution of intricate and dynamic behaviors. This integrated approach showcases the potential for deploying a versatile quadruped system that displays adaptivity, robustness, and a diverse repertoire of gaits through the combination of passive design principles and synergistic actuation.

3 Discussion

Quadrupedal locomotion is a topic that has long engaged and fascinated researchers in biomechanics, robotics, neuroscience and learning communities. Legged robot designers often disregard the postural couplings shown by biological animals, opting for full actuation and complex control schemes. However, animals' agile and robust performance suggests that robot designs could greatly benefit from a comprehensive understanding of complex mechanisms, and strategically designed compliance seen in the biomechanics of animals. This has the potential to simplify the required control, by offloading some computation to the body, and it is particularly relevant for achieving control decisions that must be made rapidly or even instantaneously. However, implementing such mechanisms remains a central challenge to enable leg control that is simple, fast, and cost-effective and that can begin to match the biological counterpart.

The approach we propose focuses on maximizing the behaviours and properties which can

be performed by the embodied form of the robot. Specifically, we show that by integrating adaptive synergies, not can we reduce the number of actuators required to control the robotic structure, but can also enhance the adaptability and the robustness of interactions between the robot and the environment. By developing PAWS, the first synergy based free-standing quadruped, we highlight the potential of this approach, and how it can be used to underpin the design of future quadrupeds.

The proposed robotic design approach facilitates the design of robotic structures that demonstrate bio-inspired mechanical recovery strategies, offering particular benefits for navigating uneven, unpredictable, or soft terrains. By utilizing the biologically relevant poses, the joint stiffness can be designed to reflect the interaction impedance used by animals when interacting with the environment. Further research is required to fully understand how variable stiffness analysis can be translated to robotic systems to enable body-driven animal locomotion. In addition, the wider benefits of this approach need to be explored, for example analysis of the efficiency, or cost of transport of the robot.

4 Methods

4.1 Animal motion analysis

The openly available dataset from which we extract the synergies is 30 minutes of motion capture footage of a dog recorded on flat terrain (42). The data itself is unstructured and contains various canine gaits, including walk, pace, trot, and canter, as well as sitting, standing, lying, jumping, and idling. To facilitate analysis and interpretation, a skeleton model composed of 27 bones and 81 degrees of freedom was fitted to the captured data (42). This skeleton model allows us to analyze the kinematics of the dog thoroughly.

The angles of the 12 joints in the dog's limbs were extracted by analyzing skeleton motion files at different time frames. To do this, the joints' markers were connected with segments,

and the relative angles between each consecutive segment were obtained. Specifically, the evolutions of the shoulder, elbow, and carpal (wrist) joints were extracted for the forelimbs, while the evolutions of the hip, stifle (knee), and tarsal (ankle) joints were extracted for the hindlimbs. This analysis covered a total of 147,541 video frames.

To obtain the paw trajectories in 2D, the position of the distal marker linked to the front and back paws is tracked over time in the sagittal plane and transformed relative to the marker tracking the dog’s base at the sacrum.

4.2 Synergy formulation and optimization method

A general animal or robotic kinematic structure can be defined by a vector of n joint angles, $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$. A postural synergy base is an orthogonal base of the joint space (48), described by a matrix $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. This allows the structure’s configuration to be described by the vector $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^n$, as $q = S\sigma$. Each column of S represents a coordinated motion in joint space, also referred to as postural synergy. The i^{th} element of σ represents the amount of movement of the structure along the i^{th} synergy.

Several studies in the literature, especially focused on humans, have shown that biological movements can usually be accurately described with a remarkably low dimensional synergy subspace. More precisely, for the case of $k \ll n$ we can define S as,

$$q \simeq S^{(1:k)}\sigma^{(1:k)}, \quad (1)$$

where $S^{(k)}$ are the first k columns of S , $\sigma^{(1:k)}$ are the first k elements of σ , and \simeq is defined in the statistical sense. In other words, all movements observed can be explained to a certain degree by combining k fundamental motions rather than n .

We show in Sec. 2.1 that a synergistic behavior also underpins the legs of a dog while running. In our case, we selected two synergies ($k = 2$), as discussed in 2.2, however the

following analysis remains general. We refer to (49) for an analysis of the trade-off between the number of synergies and the diversity of behavior reproducible with these.

In the following, we propose a method to automatically translate the synergies extracted from data into design specifications for an artificial system. We refer to underactuated structures in the general form introduced (for robotic hands) in (50) with the generalization of the tendon routing included in (38, *Sec. III-E*). This class of under-actuation strategies (51) involves k motors whose rotation angles are the $\sigma^{(1:k)}$ in Eq. (1). Each motor is connected to a tendon that goes through the whole kinematic structure, revolving around joint-level pulleys. We collect the radii of these pulleys in a matrix $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k}$, and we call $R_{i,j}$ the radius of the pulley corresponding to the i^{th} joint and the j^{th} tendon. A linear torsional spring is placed parallel to each joint. The stiffness of the spring acting on the i^{th} joint is $\kappa_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and the complete vector is $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Fig. 2c shows an example of such a mechanism. We propose here to automatically identify and set the optimal stiffnesses k , pulley sizes R , and tendon routing ρ for a desired synergy $\hat{S}^{(1:k)}$ by solving the following nonlinear mixed-integer optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned}
& \arg \min_{\substack{\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^k, R \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times k} \\ \rho \in \{-1,0,1\}^{n \times k}}} \|\hat{S}^{(1:k)} - (R \circ \rho)_{\text{diag}\{\kappa\}}^+\|_{\text{F}}^2 \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad \kappa^- \leq \kappa_i \leq \kappa^+, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\
& \quad \quad r^- \leq R_{i,j} \leq r^+, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}, j \in \{1, \dots, k\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The minimum and maximum allowed stiffnesses are κ^-, κ^+ , and the minimum and maximum allowed radii of the pulleys are r^-, r^+ . Here, $\rho_{i,j}$ defines if the tendon is routed counterclockwise, not routed, or routed clockwise around the pulley $R_{i,j}$. The symbol \circ is the Hadamard product of the two matrices, also called the element-wise product. The symbol $(\cdot)_E^+$ refers to the *Moore-Penrose Pseudoinverse* of the argument weighted through the matrix E . Finally, $\|\cdot\|_{\text{F}}$ is the Frobenious norm of the argument, so the cost function is the squared Frobenious distance between the desired synergy matrix $\hat{S}^{(1:k)}$ and $(R \circ \rho)_{\text{diag}\{\kappa\}}^+$.

In the following, we show that $(R \circ \rho)_{\text{diag}\{\kappa\}}^+$ is the synergy matrix of the mechanical system

with physical characteristics κ, R, ρ , thus justifying the definition of the cost function in Eq. (2). These derivations are akin to the ones proposed for robotic hands in (38, 50).

Call the tendon positions $x \in \mathbb{R}^k$, then by using kineto-static duality, the torque vector τ at the joints and the tendon tension vector τ_M are related by $\tau = (R \circ \rho)^\top \tau_M$. By including a linear elastic force arising from the springs at the joints ($\text{diag}\{\kappa\}q$), the equilibrium of the joint torques is achieved. If no external forces are considered, the static solution can be written as $(R \circ \rho)^\top \tau_M = \text{diag}\{\kappa\}q$. By solving for q it yields to $q = \text{diag}\{\kappa\}^{-1} R^\top ((R \circ \rho) \text{diag}\{\kappa\}^{-1} (R \circ \rho)^\top)^{-1} x$. Finally, recalling the definition of *weighted Moore-Penrose pseudoinverse* and that the motor state is our synergy reference variable (i.e., $x = \sigma$), yields the desired relation $S = (R \circ \rho)_{\text{diag}\{\kappa\}}^+$.

Each synergy is actuated in planar motion by an actuator (Dynamixel XL430-W250-T) fixed to the body of the robot, pulling on a tendon that is attached at the very tip of the limb on an axle (see Fig. 1a for a picture of the setup). Hence, for two synergies, two motors are used, one on each side of the leg, leading to a total of four motors for the full system.

A set of independently actuated tendons, guided by pulleys, running along joints with the stiffness specified in E , is proposed to translate animal movement to a robotic structure, such as in Fig. 9.

4.3 Robot prototype

PAWS is composed of two half-bodies, making it symmetric with respect to the sagittal plane. The robot's design parameters are provided in Fig. 9a. The joints, pulleys of the transmission system and the central body are 3D printed from PLA on a 3D printer (Prusa Mk-3). Each half-body is driven by two actuated tendons, each corresponding to a synergy. Two motors (Dynamixel XL430-W250-T) actuate each synergy. The robot's rigid links are connected via ball bearings to a central shaft providing robustness and are also connected via screws to each

modular torsional spring module.

4.3.1 Modular design set

To translate synergies into optimized design specifications we create a modular design that has the following components:

- Links, which serve as the foundation of the robotic structure and feature a tunable rest position that can be adjusted in 45° increments. They are machined in aluminum using CNC technology for precise and accurate fabrication. The lengths of the links are parameterized so to reflect the animal skeleton and its kinematics.
- Torsional stiffness joint modules composed of two antagonistic linear springs, a tray and a pulley, which are responsible for providing compliance to the robotic structure as specified by the optimal E matrix. These modules feature tunable torsional stiffness that can be adjusted linearly from 325 to 1092 N.mm/rad by increasing the radius r of the stiffness pulley according to Eq. (3) presented in the next Sec. 4.3.2.
- Tendons, which are responsible for the control of the robotic structure and transmit the force from the motors to the joints. The tendons used are metal with a diameter of 0.4 mm.
- Guiding pulleys, which are responsible for controlling the motion ratios of the robotic structure at the joints.
- Feet, which provide floor contact and stability. Balls are cast in Dragon Skin™ 20 silicon to create compliant and high-friction feet.

Ball bearings are used in all rotational contacts, to reduce friction, and thus, increase the efficiency and performance of the robotic structure. Aluminum rods are used at each joint along

with 3D-printed mechanical stoppers to hold the modules together. Fig. 2c shows a render of the assembled view of a three-jointed leg structure using the aforementioned modules. The components are carefully designed and tested to work together in a synergistic manner, resulting in an optimized and highly efficient robotic structure that can be easily resized and customized for a wide range of animal structures.

4.3.2 Revolute joint design

The need for both joint rotation and tunable torsional stiffness in a revolute joint design prompted the creation of a stiffness module incorporating linear springs. The mechanism employs a central *stiffness pulley* that facilitates rotational motion, with wires attached on two opposite ends. Simultaneously, two linear springs act antagonistically to provide stiffness in both directions as illustrated in Fig. 2d. This design enables a large range of possible stiffnesses by using a pulley reduction with a ratio of 2:1 to maximize the range of stiffness achievable within the linear region of the spring. The modules can be stacked onto the joint, and cause them to have a torsional stiffness resulting from the linear stiffness in the modules.

The torsional stiffness k_θ can be calculated by computing the moment at the joint per angle of rotation when the 2 springs are acting (see Fig. 2d for free body diagrams):

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_\theta &= -\frac{dM}{d\theta} = -\frac{d[(F^- - F^+)r]}{d\theta} = -\frac{(-\frac{k dl}{2} - \frac{k dl}{2})r}{d\theta} = \frac{kr}{2} \frac{dl}{d\theta} \\
 k_\theta &= \frac{1}{2}kr^2, \text{ since } dl = rd\theta
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

With this result, the design enables quadratic scaling of stiffness through the r^2 term. Thanks to the quadratic relation, the stiffness module is able to vary the stiffness across a wide range with small changes in the pulley radius. This feature, combined with the 2:1 pulley system enables a wide range of achievable stiffnesses within the linear region of the deformation of the springs.

4.4 Simulation environment

A simulation environment was built in MATLAB to efficiently test and validate the methods. The simulation calculates and reproduces the motion under tendon actuation of a single limb formed by a series of links, with pulleys of different sizes, and joints of different stiffnesses.

The simulator also contains an optimizer that uses a genetic algorithm to minimize Eq. (2). For a given number of synergies, the genetic algorithm returns the different design specifications for E and R , namely the pulley radii, tendon routing, and joint stiffnesses and visualizes each synergy in action.

Two examples of 3-link designs generated by the optimizer from a given synergy matrix are reported in the Supplementary Fig. S8. Thanks to this analysis it is possible to visualize the excellent mappings between the desired postural synergies and the simple mechanisms generated. Each synergy is independently actuated by the same amount, to demonstrate the resulting motion.

4.5 Inverse kinematic in synergy space

Fig. 3 shows that the first two synergies of the biological quadruped are sufficient to generate paw evolution necessary to perform a number of motions - such as walking, running, and sitting. Here we describe the strategy that we used to obtain the low dimensional synergy inputs $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^2$ that match the natural data. The same algorithm is also used to generate the gaits of PAWS. Note that since the two left and two right legs are separately actuated, we consider them separately when solving the inverse kinematic problem. First, we pre-processed the animal data and projected each of the 2 end effector positions of fore and hindlimbs acquired with Motion Capture $x_{3D} \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$ into the dog's sagittal plane, resulting $x \in \mathbb{R}^6$.

Next, we use a Jacobian-based kinematic inversion. However, the standard approach would result in joint space configurations q and not in commands in synergy space σ . Instead, we

borrow a variation on the method developed within the continuum robotics field, which operates a direct task to actuators inversion (52), and we adapt it to synergistic actuation. Call $x = f_x(q)$ the standard forward kinematics mapping the joint coordinates q in the end effector locations x . We then recall from Sec. 4.2 that the actuator’s kinematics are $q = S\sigma$, with $S = (R \circ \rho)_{\text{diag}\{\kappa\}}^+$. Combining the two maps yields $x = f_x(S\sigma)$. This composed end-to-end forward kinematics has the Jacobian $J(\sigma) = J_x(S\sigma)S$, with J_x being the Jacobian of f_x . Thus J is such that $\dot{x} = J\dot{\sigma}$.

Having a well-defined differential map, we can then use the following kinematic inversion scheme to find the $\bar{\sigma}$ such that $\|\bar{x} - f_x(S\bar{\sigma})\|_2^2$ is minimum, for any given \bar{x} :

$$\dot{\bar{\sigma}} = \alpha(J_x(S\bar{\sigma})S)^+(\bar{x} - f_x(S\bar{\sigma})), \quad (4)$$

where α is a scalar gain. Note that, for the placing of both feet with two synergies, $J_x \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 2}$ has more rows than columns. This property indicates that the problem is kinematically underactuated, and only a two-dimensional submanifold of the space of all feet postures can be realized precisely. The good performance that is achieved when realizing gaits is therefore a property of the proposed S , which spans the configurations necessary to make this manifold coincide with the feet configurations used by the dog.

4.6 Stiffness ellipsoid simulation

Fig. 10 shows the stiffness of ellipsoids at different points in Cartesian space. Simulated and experimental results demonstrate the variation of stiffnesses across the workspace. To model and evaluate the Cartesian stiffness of the structure in Cartesian space for a given pose, i.e. $\bar{q} = S\bar{\sigma}$, we must first estimate the stiffness at the joint level, and then map it to Cartesian space. The compliance of the structure at joint level C_q , i.e. the inverse of the stiffness (38), can be found from physical parameters as:

$$C_q = E^{-1} - E^{-1}R^T(RE^{-1}R^T)^{-1}RE^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

To obtain $\bar{q} = S\bar{\sigma}$ the solution of the inverse kinematic problem in 2.3, the Cartesian compliance (53) at the end effector takes the form,

$$C_x = J(\bar{q})C_{\bar{q}}J(\bar{q})^\top; \quad (6)$$

This analysis can be performed in both simulations and on the real robot.

4.7 Experimental setup

The experimental setup used for the experiments presented in Sec. 2.4 and 2.6, shown in Fig. 5a was developed to assess the robot’s response to environmental excitations. Inspired by the experimental setup developed in (28), the platform is composed of a treadmill (Gonser Walking Pad) with adjustable speeds and a guiding system composed of a four-bar linkage. The treadmill settings were adjusted to achieve speeds ranging from 1 to 6 km/h in 0.5 km/h increments. Alternatively, for slower speeds, the treadmill speed was directly connected to a power supply voltage, thus controlling the speed by varying the input current. To constrain the robot’s movements to the sagittal plane, a four-bar mechanism was designed to connect the robot’s body to a fixed frame. These links of the mechanism were utilized to support a counterweight, ranging from 1.5 to 3 kg, for the half-body and the four-legged body respectively. The mechanism was connected to a metallic frame, which was securely attached to the ceiling. This configuration allowed for a pendulum-like movement, effectively constraining pitching and restricting the robot to translations in the sagittal plane (fore-aft and up-down). As the synergy analysis was performed on the sagittal plane of animals, this setup proved particularly suitable for testing emerging passive motions. To test active motions, two Dynamixel XL430-W250-T motors were used for each half-body. These motors were connected at the base to control each synergy using two tendons, accommodating both positive and negative directions. The contributions of both motors were linearly combined to generate the desired motions. Control signals were transmitted to the motors through the Dynamixel motor controller through Dynamixel Python

SDK. The motor controller was powered by a dedicated power supply, thus requiring external power to actuate the robotic system.

In the free-body experiments shown in Fig. 6c, the robot was left without any gravity compensation or stabilizing mechanism, but it was connected to the external power supply and to an external computer to send the motor activation commands. In the free-walking experiment in Fig. 6e, the robot was loosely connected to an external tendon to provide stabilizing support during the locomotion gait.

4.8 Computer vision setup and motion tracking techniques

To analyze the movement of the limbs in the sagittal plane of the real system, recorded videos were post-processed using *Kinovea* (54), an open-source motion tracking software. The software facilitated the analysis of the joint angle evolutions over time from the recorded videos. Additionally, *Kinovea* allowed for the tracing and extraction of the trajectories of the limb's end effector, from which the Cartesian pose could be extracted in either the robot or world frame coordinates.

In all experiments, a camera (Logitech Brio 500) was placed perpendicularly to the plane of analysis, at a significant distance with respect to the displacements under measure, to minimize distortions arising in the pixels-to-meters mapping. The calibration of coordinates from pixels to millimeters was found by measuring the pixel length corresponding to the known distance of 320 mm between the hip joint and the shoulder joint of the robot in the video footage. This measurement served as a calibration factor, and all pixel lengths were multiplied by this factor to obtain the corresponding millimeter measurements.

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Author contributions statement

F.S.: conceptualization, synergy theory and simulation, hardware design and experiments, writing, review & editing, result analysis and visualization;

M.M.A: hardware design and experiments, motion data extraction and analysis, result analysis and visualization, writing, review & editing;

C.D.S.: conceptualization, experiment design, supervision, writing, review & editing;

J.H.: conceptualization, experiment design, writing review & editing, supervision, funding acquisition;

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability statement

The code and data developed for this work are available at <https://github.com/fstella97/PAWS.git>.

Description of Additional Supplementary Files

The following videos are attached to support the results presented in the article

Supplementary Video 1. [[Link](#)]

Description: Single synergy activations and reachable workspace (Fig. 9b-d)

Supplementary Video 2. [[Link](#)]

Description: Passive locomotion excitation - half and full robot at different speeds (Fig. 4)

Supplementary Video 3. [[Link](#)]

Description: Passive response to disturbances - half and full robot overcoming obstacles and recovering from mechanical perturbations (Fig. 5)

Supplementary Video 4. [[Link](#)]

Description: Stiffness and mechanical couplings experiment (Fig. 10)

Supplementary Video 5. [[Link](#)]

Description: Combination of active and passive behaviors for jumping gaits (Fig. 6d)

Supplementary Video 6. [[Link](#)]

Description: Actuated behavior diversity - full robot (Fig. 6c-e)

5 Supplementary materials

5.1 Joint mechanical characterization

To validate the joint model presented in Fig. 2d, first, a single linear spring was characterized, then the full joint stiffness was evaluated to include the compliance of the transmission system.

To validate the linear springs, a ZwickRoell materials testing machine was used (Fig. 7-1). The force response per unit of linear deformation was recorded in the experiment. The spring constant was calculated to be $k = 2.89$ N/mm and was strictly linear ($R^2 = 0.9999$). By plugging in the linear stiffness in (3), a 45.5 mm diameter stiffness pulley results in a torsional stiffness of $k_{\theta}^{(2)} = 747.88$ N.mm/rad. When a single spring is acting, this stiffness further reduces to $k_{\theta}^{(1)} = 373.94$ N.mm/rad.

Now, the joint with a stiffness pulley with a diameter of 45.5 mm was characterized using the setup in Fig. 7-2, which involved clamping one end of the joint to a bench vise, suspending a known mass m at the other end at $L = 130$ mm, and measuring the angular deformation $\Delta\theta$ using a protractor. The torque is reported at the joint per unit of angular deformation using $\tau = mgL \cos \Delta\theta$. Two linear regimes were observed in Fig. 7-3, one where both springs are acting in tension on the joint and one where a single spring is in tension. The slope of a curve represents the torsional stiffness during a certain regime: $k_{\theta}^{(2)} = 561.3$ N.mm/rad and $k_{\theta}^{(1)} = 304.2$ N.mm/rad. A difference of 25% and 19%, respectively, with the theoretical values can be noted, which can be explained by friction losses in the transmission, compliance in the wires of the stiffness module and nonlinear deformation of the springs.

5.2 Link between mechanism properties and kinematic joint evolution

Two examples of 3-link designs generated by the optimizer from an exemplary synergy matrix are rendered in the simulation environment in Fig. 8. Each synergy is independently actuated for the same amount of tendon activation to demonstrate the resulting motion.

Figure 7: **Supplementary Figure.** 1. Tensile testing of the linear spring stiffness k using a ZwickRoell materials testing machine. 2. Experimental setup to evaluate the torsional stiffness k_{θ} of the joint. 3. Joint stiffness characterization curve (Diameter = 45.5 mm stiffness pulley).

Figure 8: **Supplementary Figure.** Examples of optimized mechanisms for simple synergy matrices

Figure 9: **Supplementary Figure.** **a)** A representation of the mechanism found as a solution of the optimization, considering tendon routing, pulley sizes and stiffness at the joint level. **b)** At the top, the evolution of the first two principal components, described as Synergy 1 and 2, as extracted from PCA. In the middle, the evolution of the two synergies after the optimization, i.e. considering the losses due to the mechanical design specifications, but not considering the deployment on a real system. At the bottom, the evolution shown by the real system when actuating only one of the motors. **a)** Relative activation ratio between joint angles during the three design stages. By comparing the three it is possible to observe small relative error accumulation in the design process. **b)** The workspace achievable with a combination of the two synergies.

Figure 10: **Supplementary Figure** Images of the stiffness and coupling experiments. **a)** Experimental setup with the rigid manipulator, connected to the robot’s paw. The robotic system is placed at zero activation level for both synergies. The experiment is repeated for 36 different goal positions and stiffnesses. The stiffness ellipsoids evaluated from the experiment are plotted and compared to simulated gaits. **b)** Mechanical couplings between the legs show very diverse induced displacements by triggering different external displacements. These are especially useful for compensatory strategies.

Supplementary Files

This is a list of supplementary files associated with this preprint. Click to download.

- [Movie1.mp4](#)
- [Movie2.mp4](#)
- [Movie3.mp4](#)
- [Movie4.mp4](#)
- [Movie5.mp4](#)
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